

Supplement: Highly Sensitive Persons feel more emotionally lonely than the general population

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Social isolation

A) *How often do you meet with close family members who do not live with you?*

Infrequent meetings:

- 1) less than once a year or never
- 2) once or twice a year
- 3) once every few months

Frequent meetings:

- 4) once or twice a month
- 5) once or twice a week
- 6) three or more times a week

B) *How often do you meet with friends?*

Infrequent meetings:

- 1) less than once a year or never
- 2) once or twice a year
- 3) once every few months

Frequent meetings:

- 4) once or twice a month
- 5) once or twice a week
- 6) three or more times a week

C) *Please indicate the number of people you can contact for practical help*

Small social network:

- 1) none
- 2) one to two
- 3) three to four

Large social network:

- 4) five to nine
- 5) ten and more

D) *How many really close friends do you have?*

Small social network:

- 1) none
- 2) one to two
- 3) three to four

Large social network:

- 4) five to nine
- 5) ten and more

E) How many other friends you have?

Small social network:

- 1) none
- 2) one to five
- 3) six to nine

Large social network:

- 4) ten to nineteen
- 5) twenty and more